

Synthesis and structure of some novel Schiff base complexes with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}

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Abstract : The chemistry of metal complexes with tailor made Schiff base ligands and their applications, have aroused considerable interest mainly because of preparative accessibility, diverse reactivity and structural variability. Complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with the Schiff bases viz. 3,4-dichloroaniline with 2-furfuraldehyde/4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and 3-chloro-4-fluoroaniline with 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde have been synthesized. Physico-chemical characterization of the complexes have been done with the help of micro-analytical data, UV-Vis, FT-IR, ESR spectroscopy, molar conductance, thermal analysis, FAB-mass and magnetic susceptibility measurements. FAB-mass and thermal data show degradation pattern of complexes. All the complexes are colored and stable. The complexes exhibit coordination number to be 4 and 6.

Keywords : Synthesis, FAB-mass, IR, UV, ESR, thermal analyses.

Introduction

Preparation of the new ligands is perhaps the most important step in the development of metal complexes, which exhibit unique desired properties and novel reactivity¹. The chemistry of metal complexes with tailor made Schiff base ligands and their application, have aroused considerable interest mainly because of preparative accessibility, diverse reactivity and structural variability. Metal complexes of Schiff bases have played a central role in the development of coordination chemistry³ and have many applications in various fields. Such ligands and their metal complexes have a variety of applications in biology and industry due to their role in catalysis and organic synthesis⁵. In present paper, the synthesis and characterization of the complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} involving the Schiff base ligands derived from 3,4-dichloroaniline with 2-furfuraldehyde/4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and 3-chloro-4-fluoroaniline with 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde have been reported.

Results and discussion

All the metal complexes are colored, solid and stable towards air and moisture at room temperature. They decompose at high temperature on heating. The analytical

data of the complexes are consistent with the proposed molecular formula shown in Table 1. The metal complexes exhibit 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry.

FAB Mass :

The FAB mass spectrum gives additional structural information about the analyzed species⁶. The FAB mass spectrum of [Ni(DCA)₂Cl₂].2H₂O complex shown a molecular ion peak (M⁺) *m/z* = 751.7 amu; which suggest the monomeric nature of the complex. The spectrum of the complex also shows a series of peaks corresponding to various fragments. Their intensity gives an idea about stability of the fragments. On the basis of above, stoichiometry may be suggested for the complexes.

IR spectra :

The data of the IR spectra of Schiff base ligand and its metal complexes are listed in Table 2. The IR spectra of the complexes were compared with those of the free ligand in order to determine the involvement of coordination sites in chelation. Characteristic peaks in the spectra of the ligand and complexes were considered and compared.

The IR spectra of the ligand FCA exhibit band at about 1620 cm⁻¹ (merg) due to the C=N (azomethine)

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of ligands and metal complexes

Compd./ Mol. wt.	Colour	M.p. (dec) (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :			μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Ω_m (Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	Yield (%)
			Found/Calcd.					
			C	H	N			
FCA [C ₁₁ H ₇ NOCl ₂] 240.0	Light brown	120	55.05 (55.00)	2.80 (2.91)	5.80 (5.83)	-	-	68
[Ni(C ₁₁ H ₇ NOCl ₂) ₂ Cl ₂ . 2H ₂ O 645.7	Black	325	40.43 (40.88)	2.73 (2.78)	5.10 (4.33)	Diamag.	98.9	80
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₇ NOCl ₂) ₂ Cl ₂] 614.5	Brown	130	42.90 (42.94)	2.20 (2.27)	4.66 (4.55)	2.30	24.8	78
DCA [C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₂] 293.0	Light yellow	135	61.39 (61.43)	4.72 (4.77)	9.50 (9.55)	-	-	80
[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₂) ₂ Cl ₂ . 2H ₂ O 751.7	Yellow	110	47.86 (47.89)	4.20 (4.25)	7.27 (7.44)	Diamag.	55.6	70
[Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₂) ₂ Cl ₂] 720.5	Black	112	48.90 (49.96)	3.77 (3.88)	7.43 (7.77)	1.86	52.2	75
DFA [C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ ClF] 276.5	Light dirty green	95	65.00 (65.09)	5.00 (5.06)	9.92 (10.12)	-	-	87
[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ ClF) ₂ Cl ₂ . 2H ₂ O 718.7	Yellow	145	50.00 (50.10)	4.42 (4.45)	7.20 (7.79)	Diamag.	14.9	82
[Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ ClF) ₂ Cl ₂ . H ₂ O 705.5	Dark green	260	51.04 (51.02)	4.22 (4.25)	7.50 (7.93)	1.89	48.6	78

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) of ligand and its complexes

Compd.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
FCA	1620(merg)	1210(m)	-	-	-
[Ni(FCA) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	1595(merg)	1175(m)	3381(br)	515(w)	480(w)
[Cu(FCA) ₂ Cl ₂]	1596(merg)	1171(m)	-	510(w)	490(w)
DCA	1578(s)	-	-	-	-
[Ni(DCA) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	1550(m)	-	3366(br)	-	492(w)
[Cu(DCA) ₂ Cl ₂]	1542(m)	-	-	-	485(w)
DFA	1579(s)	-	-	-	-
[Ni(DFA) ₂ Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	1560(m)	-	3350(br)	-	490(w)
[Cu(DFA) ₂ Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	1565(m)	-	3356(br)	-	495(w)

group. This band is shifted to lower frequency by 15–20 cm⁻¹ in the complexes (appears slightly merged with benzene ring) showing its participation in chelation through the azomethine nitrogen^{7–12}. The lowering is due to re-

duction of electron density in the azomethine link. The medium intensity band observed at 1210 cm⁻¹ is assignable to C–O–C (ring stretching). This band undergo negative shift (by 15–20 cm⁻¹) in complexes suggesting the

Note

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal complexes of FCA.

Fig. 2. Proposed structure of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal complexes of DFA.

Fig. 3. Proposed structure of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal complexes of DCA.

involvement of oxygen of C-O-C moiety in coordination with metal ion¹³. A broad band around $3381 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectrum of Ni^{II} complex, is assignable to ν_{stre} of water. This band has been found absent in the Cu^{II} complex. The new bands in the spectra of complexes at 515

$\pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $480 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been assigned to $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ bonding, respectively.

The IR spectrum of ligand DCA shows a band at 1578 cm^{-1} due to (C=N) azomethine group, which shifts down ($1542 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes. The negative shift

indicates the participation of azomethine group in complexation¹⁴. In the Schiff base two chloro groups at 3,4-position are present in one part (3,4-dichloroaniline) of the ligand. The chloro groups are the electron withdrawing and have negative inductive effect, thus basicity of the ligand gets affected. Here, the Schiff base (ligand) behaves as monodentate. The IR spectrum of Ni^{II} complex exhibit new band around $3366 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ν_{stre} of water. This band has been found absent in the Cu^{II} complex. The new bands ($485 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes have tentatively been assigned to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ bonding.

The IR spectrum of ligand DFA shows a band at 1579 cm^{-1} due to C=N (azomethine) group. This shifts down ($1565 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes. The negative shift indicates the participation of azomethine group in complexation. The appearance of broad band around $3356 \pm 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of complexes may be due to ν_{stre} water molecule. The new band observed in the spectra of complexes at 495 cm^{-1} has been assigned to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ bonding¹⁴.

Electronic spectra and magnetic behavior of complexes :

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded at room temperature using methanol as solvent.

The absorption spectrum of Ni^{II} complex of FCA shows, two bands at 12406 and 21231 cm^{-1} which have been assigned to ${}^1A_{1g}^{-1}E_g$ (ν_1) and ${}^1A_{1g}^{-1}B_{2g}$ (ν_2) transitions, respectively. The diamagnetic nature of the complex and the above transitions suggest the geometry to be square planar. The Cu^{II} complex of FCA show a broad band at $12520\text{--}16210 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is assignable to ${}^2E_g\text{--}{}^2T_{2g}$ transition. The value of ligand field parameters viz. $10 Dq$, λ and LFSE are as 12520 , $(-)$ 206 cm^{-1} and $89.74 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. These parameters suggest the octahedral geometry for this Cu^{II} complex. The magnetic moment is 2.30 B.M. The magnetic moment value (2.30) obtained is higher than the spin only value (1.7 B.M.) indicating greater orbital contribution and distortion of octahedral geometry.

The electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex of DCA shows two bands at 12416 and 22341 cm^{-1} , which have been assigned to ${}^1A_{1g}^{-1}E_g$ and ${}^1A_{1g}^{-1}B_{2g}$ transitions, respectively. This complex is diamagnetic in nature. Therefore, a square planar geometry has been suggested. Cu^{II} com-

plex gives bands at 12318 and 18021 cm^{-1} , which are assignable to ${}^2B_{1g}\text{--}{}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g}\text{--}{}^2E_g$ transitions. Its magnetic moment is 1.86 B.M. This favors the square planar stereo-arrangement.

The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complex gives two peaks around 12345 and 20115 cm^{-1} due to ${}^1A_{1g}^{-1}E_g$ and ${}^1A_{1g}^{-1}B_{2g}$ transitions, respectively. This complex is diamagnetic; hence the spatial arrangement of this complex is square planar. Two absorption bands at 12531 and 18885 cm^{-1} in the Cu^{II} complex have tentatively been assigned to ${}^2B_{1g}\text{--}{}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g}\text{--}{}^2E_g$ transitions. Its magnetic moment is 1.89 B.M. This suggests the geometry to be square planar¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

ESR spectra :

The spectra of Cu^{II} complex have been recorded on X-band at frequency 9.5 GHz under the magnetic field strength 3400 Gauss . The values of ESR parameters of Cu^{II}-FCA complex viz. g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , Δg and G are as 2.2291 , 2.0663 , 2.1206 , 0.16276 , and 3.5292 respectively. The parameter g_{av} was obtained by equation $[(g_{\text{av}}) = 1/3 (2g_{\perp} + g_{\parallel})]$. The g -tensor values of Cu^{II} complex can be used to derive the ground state. The value of $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ in the complex, suggest that the unpaired electron is localized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. The value of g_{\parallel} for the Cu^{II} complex indicates the prevalence of covalent character in the metal-ligand bond. The g values are related to the axial symmetry parameter G by the Hathway expression $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)^{20,21}$.

According to Hathway if the value of G is greater than four ($G > 4$), the exchange interaction is negligible. Whereas when the value of G is less than 4 ($G < 4$) a considerable exchange interaction is indicated in the complex. The G value of 3.5292 indicates considerable exchange interaction of Cu-Cu in the complex¹⁹⁻²¹.

Thermal analyses :

The thermogram of the Cu^{II} complex of FCA (Fig. 4) show no loss in weight up to $140 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, indicating the absence of any water in the complex. On increasing the temperature above $140 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, a weight loss at faster rate occurs up to $370 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which corresponded with the decomposition of the ligand moiety. After $370 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, a weight has been observed in general upto $570 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. A horizontal zone beyond $570 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ suggests the formation of ultimate pyrolysis product as metal oxide (Remaining wt% obsd./ calcd. $29/26.77$)²²⁻²⁴.

Fig. 4. Thermogram of the Cu^{II} complex of FCA.

The thermal degradation behavior of the complexes of DCA and DFA has been studied (as heated in muffle furnace for 35–40 min) at three temperatures (100 °C, 400 °C and 600 °C) in the atmosphere of air.

The Ni^{II} complex of DCA have been studied at three temperatures. The remaining weight at 100 °C corresponds to loss of lattice water molecules from complex (Remaining wt% obsd./calcd. 96.25/95.21). The weight measured after heating at 400 °C indicates loss of non-coordinated part of the ligand (Remaining wt% obsd./calcd. 54.51/49.78). The weight of pyrolysis product at 600 °C corresponds to metal oxide, as an ultimate product (Remaining wt% obsd./calcd. 24.5/20.14)^{22,23}.

The Ni^{II} complex of DFA have been studied at three temperatures. The remaining weight at 100 °C corresponds to loss of lattice water molecules from complex (Remaining wt% obsd./calcd. 95.50/94.99). The weight measured after heating at 400 °C indicates loss of non-coordinated part of the ligand (Remaining wt% obsd./calcd. 60.2/52.31). The weight of pyrolysis product at 600 °C corresponds to metal oxide, as an ultimate product (Remaining wt% obsd./calcd. 22.50/17.42)^{22,23}.

Experimental

Material and methods :

All the used chemicals and metal salts were of A.R.

grade. The percentage of N, were estimated micro-analytically from SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow. Electronic spectra (in MeOH) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Lamda-2B-spectrophotometer. IR spectra (in KBr) were recorded at SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow. ESR spectra were recorded at SAIF, IIT, Mumbai. Molar conductance ($10^{-3} M$) was measured at room temperature by Elico Conductivity Bridge. FAB mass spectra were recorded at SAIF, CDRI, Lucknow. TG analysis was carried out under nitrogen atmosphere with a heating rate $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ on Mettler Toledo Star Thermal Analyzer at NIPER, Chandigarh.

Synthesis of Schiff bases :

The Schiff bases (FCA, DCA, DFA) have been synthesized by refluxing methanolic solution of 3,4-dichloroaniline with methanolic solution of 2-furfuraldehyde/4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and 3-chloro-4-fluoroaniline (methanolic solution) with 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in 1 : 1 ratio, on the water bath for about 6–7 h. The condensation product was filtered, thoroughly washed with ethanol and ether, re-crystallized with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 . The purity of the synthesized compounds was monitored by TLC using silica gel G.

Preparation of metal complexes :

The metal complexes have been prepared by mixing

the methanolic solution of respective metal salt ($MCl_2 \cdot nH_2O$) $M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ to the methanolic solution of Schiff bases (FCA, DCA, DFA) in 1 : 2 metal ligand ratio. The resulting mixture was refluxed on water-bath for 7–10 h. A colored product appeared on standing and cooling the refluxate. The precipitated complex was filtered and washed with ethanol and ether. The complexes were finally recrystallised with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous $CaCl_2$, in a desiccator.

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